

Synthesis of Coumarins in Search of Better Nonpeptidic HIV Protease Inhibitors[†]

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Manuscript received 7 August 1998

3-Substituted-4-hydroxycoumarins have been recently identified as active nonpeptidic HIV protease inhibitors. In order to get more potent inhibitors, synthesis of a number of 3-substituted-4-hydroxycoumarins have been designed. Nucleophilicity of C-3 in 4-hydroxycoumarin is exploited by reacting with an electrophile 3-carbethoxycoumarin to achieve a new C-3 substituted-4-hydroxycoumarin. But the product identified is a benzopyranodicoumarin (2), which is also obtained by the reaction of 4-hydroxycoumarin with salicylaldehyde. However, the reaction of 4-hydroxycoumarin with a number of 2-oxygenated aldehydes 4b-e affords dicoumarols (5a-d) only. On the contrary, with 2,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde (4f), a benzopyranodicoumarin (6a) is formed. The reaction of 4-hydroxycoumarin with 6-bromo-3,4-methylenedioxybenzaldehyde (4g) and 6-bromo-3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (4h), when treated separately, furnishes benzopyranodicoumarin (6b) and benzopyranocoumarin (7) respectively. In both the cases, unusual nucleophilic aromatic substitution of bromine occurs in electron-rich aromatic systems without any catalyst.

A number of coumarins have diverse biological activities¹. Osthol, alloimperatorin, isopimpinellin possess antimicrobial properties. Among a number of furocoumarins, viz. xanthotoxin, imperatorin, psoralene, angelicin, the most potent therapeutic agent is psoralene in the restoration of melanin depleted skin, i.e. in the treatment² of vitiligo and psoriasis. The oestrogenic activities of coumestans³ and the insecticidal properties of rotenoids⁴ are well-established. Phytoalexin activities are associated with the 3-aryl-4-hydroxy-1-benzopyran-2-ones⁵. In view of the structural similarities of 3-aryl-4-hydroxy-1-benzopyran-2-ones to warfarin and dicoumarol, their anticoagulant activities were investigated⁶ and several examples exhibited even stronger antivitamin K properties than dicoumarol. Coumadin⁷ (sodium warfarin) is the most widely prescribed antithrombotic in North America⁸. The major metabolites of *S*-warfarin are *S*-6-hydroxyl and *S*-7-hydroxywarfarin, which are derived by 2C9P450 isoenzyme⁹. The rapid spread of the acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) epidemic has stimulated discovery of therapeutic agents to arrest the replication¹⁰ of the causative virus, human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). One promising possibility to interrupt the viral life-cycle is the use of inhibitors of the virally encoded protease, which is indispensable for viral maturation¹¹. Among the most potent inhibitors reported thus far are the peptidomimetic compounds, but the low oral bioavailability and rapid biliary excretion of peptide-derived compounds¹² have limited their utility as potential therapeutic agents. Recently, 3-substituted-4-hydroxycoumarin compound, phenprocoumon [3-(α -ethylbenzyl)-4-hydroxycoumarin] (1) and analogous compounds have been identified as active nonpeptidic HIV protease inhibitors¹³. The biological importance and considerable therapeutic potentiality of 3-

substituted-4-hydroxycoumarins generate considerable interest¹⁴ to us in designing the synthesis of a number of 3-substituted-4-hydroxycoumarin compounds as probable HIV protease inhibitors with high therapeutic index.

The nucleophilicity of the 3-position in 4-hydroxycoumarin is well-established¹⁵. As a result, the simplest synthetic route to 3-substituted-4-hydroxycoumarin is direct alkylation at C-3. This approach was utilised in the direct coupling of 4-hydroxycoumarin with aryldiazonium salts in an acidic medium¹⁶. Coupling was also successful with organobismuth¹⁷ and organolead¹⁸ compounds. Our strategy is also to exploit the nucleophilic character of 4-hydroxycoumarin at C-3 with an electrophile like 3-carbethoxycoumarin¹⁹ to form a new carbon-carbon bond at C-3 of 4-hydroxycoumarin with C-4 of 3-carbethoxycoumarin in order to get a better nonpeptidic inhibitor of HIV protease.

An equimolecular mixture of 4-hydroxycoumarin and 3-carbethoxycoumarin in refluxing pyridine furnished a white solid in needles, m.p. 247°, after chromatographic purification. It shows λ_{\max} at 211 (log ϵ 4.65), 256 (sh. 4.07), 265 (sh. 4.02) and 305 nm (4.14). The ir spectrum exhibits bands at 1700 (C=O), 1650 (C=O), 1620 (unsaturation), 755 cm^{-1} (*ortho* disubstituted benzene). The ¹H nmr spectrum is very much interesting as it is devoid of any signal in the high field region, thus it excludes the presence of any ethyl

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on his 75th birth anniversary
666

group. It shows one proton singlet at δ 10.39 ppm, disappearing on deuteration suggesting the presence of a hydroxyl group. A two-proton multiplet near δ 7.98–8.22 ppm is characteristic for two 5-H protons of coumarin moiety. Besides these two protons, ten aromatic protons resonate as multiplets in the region of δ 7.08–7.72 ppm. A one-proton singlet at δ 5.38 ppm has also appeared. The appearance of twelve aromatic protons can only be explained by the presence of three benzene nuclei. From these spectral data, the structure **2** has been assigned as the reaction product of 4-

hydroxycoumarin and 3-carbethoxycoumarin (Scheme 1). The carbon-13 nmr spectral data and high resolution mass spectrum ($C_{25}H_{14}O_4$, m/z 410.0791, M^+) have confirmed the structure as 6-(4-hydroxycoumarin-3-yl)-6*H*,7*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-7-one (**2**). Although there is no band for hydroxyl group in the ir spectrum of **2**, it afforded a monoacetate **3** ($C_{27}H_{16}O_7$, M^+ 452), m.p. 238°, confirming the presence of a hydroxyl group in **2**. It shows an additional three proton signal in 1H nmr spectrum at δ 2.45 ppm for acetate grouping.

Scheme 1

2 : R = H

3 : R = Ac

Scheme 2

A plausible mechanism for the formation of **2** has been suggested (Scheme 2), in which nucleophilic attack of 4-hydroxycoumarin to the C-4 carbon of 3-carbethoxycoumarin takes place to furnish the expected 3-substituted-4-hydroxycoumarin. Subsequent breaking of C-3-C-4 bond of the 3-carbethoxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin moiety and Michael addition of the second molecule of 4-hydroxycoumarin afford a dicoumarol type compound. Formation of phenoxide and its nucleophilic attack to C-4 carbon of the coumarin moiety furnishes **2**. It is interesting to note that **2** does not contain any 3-carbethoxycoumarin moiety, rather a salicylaldehyde type moiety is present. So it may also be formed by the reaction of salicylaldehyde with 4-hydroxycoumarin. And this has been found so. The reaction of 4-hydroxycoumarin with salicylaldehyde **4a** in the presence of pyridine furnished **2** as only product.

Formation of a pyran ring from salicylaldehyde inspired us to carry out the reaction with a number of 2-oxygenated aromatic aldehydes (**4b-h**). However, the reactions of 4-

- 4a** $R^1=OH, R^2=R^3=R^4=H$
4b $R^1=OMe, R^2=R^3=R^4=H$
4c $R^1=OBn, R^2=R^3=R^4=H$
4d $R^1=R^3=OMe, R^2=R^4=H$
4e $R^1=R^2=R^3=OMe, R^4=H$
4f $R^1=R^3=R^4=OMe, R^2=H$
4g $R^1=Br, R^2=H, R^3, R^4=OCH_2O$
4h $R^1=Br, R^2=H, R^3=R^4=OMe$

hydroxycoumarin with the aldehydes (**4b-e**) afforded the dicoumarol derivatives (**5a-d**). On the contrary, with 2,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde **4f**, a pyranocoumarin compound, 3,4-dimethoxy-6-(4-hydroxycoumarin-3-yl)-6*H*,7*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-7-one (**6a**) was formed in which a methoxyl group had been lost. Its structure was elucidated from spectral evidences. The ir spectrum shows bands at 3300, 1690, 1660, 1630, 755 cm^{-1} . The 1H nmr spectrum exhibits a one-proton broad singlet at δ 10.30 ppm, disappearing on deuteration. This confirms the presence of one hydroxyl group in the molecule. The multiplet near δ 7.95–8.17 ppm is due to two 5'-H, 12-H protons of the coumarin nuclei. Six aromatic protons of the two coumarin moieties appear as multiplet near δ 7.24–7.66 ppm. The appearance of two one-proton singlets at δ 6.87 and 6.54

- 5a** $R^1=OMe, R^2=R^3=R^4=H$
5b $R^1=OBn, R^2=R^3=R^4=H$
5c $R^1=R^3=OMe, R^2=R^4=H$
5d $R^1=R^2=R^3=OMe, R^4=H$

ppm are due to two protons of the phenyl ring. A one-proton singlet at δ 5.33 ppm is related to the methine proton. But the most interesting feature of the spectrum is the appearance of two three-proton singlets at δ 3.93 and 3.78

- 6a** $R^1=R^2=OMe$
6b $R^1, R^2=OCH_2O$

ppm indicating the presence of only two methoxy groups in **6a**, although the starting aldehyde **4f** had three methoxy groups at 2,4,5-positions of the phenyl ring. Carbon-13 nmr spectral data also corroborate the loss of 1*a*-OMe group and the formation of a pyran ring in **6a**.

Another interesting result was obtained when 4-hydroxycoumarin was heated with 6-bromo-3,4-methylenedioxybenzaldehyde (**4g**) in refluxing pyridine. The product **6b** obtained, is devoid of any bromine atom. In carbon-13 nmr spectrum of the bromoaldehyde (**4g**), C-3 resonates at δ 113.1 ppm. But the disappearance of the resonance at δ 113.1 ppm and concomitant appearance of a new peak at δ 98.3 ppm in the spectrum of **6b** suggest the loss of bromine atom followed by the oxygenation at C-1*a*. So the shielding of *ca* δ 14.8 ppm in chemical shift of C-2 (from δ 113.1 to 98.3 ppm) is due to the introduction of a new alkoxy group at the *ortho*-position of C-2 by substituting the bromine atom. The change of functional group from CHO to CH has very little effect (*ca.* δ 0.7 ppm) on the chemical shift of the *meta*-carbon²⁰ (at C-2). Similarly, 1H nmr chemical shift of 2-H in **6b** appears at δ 6.45 ppm, whereas in 6-bromo-3,4-methylenedioxybenzaldehyde (**4g**), the same proton resonates at δ 6.99 ppm. So a shielding of *ca.* δ 0.5 ppm of 2-H also corroborates the nucleophilic substitution of bromine

atom by alkoxy group. Thus from the spectral evidences the structure has been assigned as 3,4-methylenedioxy-6-(4-hydroxycoumarin-3-yl)-6*H*,7*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-7-one (**6b**). Nucleophilic aromatic substitution (S_NAr) of aryl halides generally occurs in the presence of electron-withdrawing groups like nitro²¹ in the aromatic system or in the presence of metal catalysts²² like copper and thallium. Even the preparation of aryloxybenzaldehyde from fluorobenzaldehyde and phenol by nucleophilic aromatic substitution in the absence of any catalyst has been reported²³. But the formation of **6b** by aromatic substitution in an electron-rich aromatic system without any catalyst is very much unusual. To the best of our knowledge this is the first example of this kind.

However, the most interesting result was observed when a mixture of 4-hydroxycoumarin and 6-bromo-3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde was heated in pyridine. From spectral analysis the structure of the product has been assigned as 3,4-dimethoxy-6*H*,7*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-7-one (**7**) in which also nucleophilic aromatic substitution of bromine has taken place. Here also formation of a pyran ring has been confirmed by the appearance of a new peak at δ 100.9 ppm in carbon-13 nmr

spectrum. But the striking structural feature of **7** is the presence of a methylene group at C-6, resonating at δ 29.6 ppm and the absence of any methine peak at that region. Formation of this reduced product under this reaction condition is also very much surprising, although bromopiperonal (**4g**) and bromoveratraldehyde (**4h**) are structurally alike. The hydroxymethylene may be converted to methylene by disproportionation reaction, although no ketonic product has been isolated. It is noteworthy to report that **7** is the only monocoumarin compound formed in this series.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary in sulphuric acid bath as well as in electrically heated metal block, and are uncorrected. Uv spectra were measured in aldehyde free ethanol on Varian 634H and Hitachi U2000 spectrophotometer. Ir spectra were run on Beckmann IR 20, Pye Unicam SP 1025 and Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometers. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ or in DMSO-d₆ using TMS

as internal standard on Varian CFT-20 and Bruker AM 300L spectrometers operating at 80 and 300 MHz respectively. Coupling constants *J*-values are given in Hz. ¹³C nmr spectra were measured in CDCl₃ or in DMSO-d₆ on Varian CFT-20 and Bruker AM 300L spectrometers operating at 20 and 75 MHz respectively with broad-band decoupling. Chemical shift values (δ relative to TMS) were assigned using CDCl₃ or DMSO-d₆ as the internal standards. Primary, secondary, tertiary and quaternary carbons were assigned by use of SFORD, APT and DEPT pulse sequences. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol JMS D300 spectrometer. Silica gel G was used as adsorbent in tlc experiments, spots were detected by staining with iodine vapour and also by exposing to uv-light. Silica gel (mesh size 60–120, BDH and Qualigen) was employed for column chromatographic separation analysis. Petroleum ether used had a boiling point range 60–80°. 2,3,4-Trimethoxybenzaldehyde and 2,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde were commercially available.

6-(4-Hydroxycoumarin-3-yl)-6*H*,7*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-7-one (**2**): A mixture of 4-hydroxycoumarin (0.162 g, 1 mmol) and 3-carbomethoxycoumarin¹⁹ (0.218 g, 1 mmol) was refluxed in dry pyridine (3 cm³) for 24 h under nitrogen atmosphere. Then pyridine was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was chromatographed over silica gel. The benzene eluted fractions afforded **2** (0.164 g, 40%) in needles, m.p. 247° (chloroform-benzene); λ_{max}/nm 211 (log ϵ 4.65), 256 (sh. 4.07), 265 (sh. 4.02), 305 (4.14); ν_{max} (KBr)/cm⁻¹ 1700, 1650, 1620, 1570, 1490, 1220, 900, 755; δ_H (CDCl₃, 80 MHz) 10.39 (1H, s, OH), 8.22–7.98 (2H, m, 5'-H, 12-H), 7.72–7.08 (10H, m, ArH), 5.38 (1H, s, 6-H); δ_C (DMSO, 20 MHz) 160.8 (C), 160.5 (C), 156.4 (C), 152.3 (C), 152.1 (C), 149.3 (C), 132.5 (CH), 132.2 (CH), 128.7 (CH), 128.4 (CH), 125.4 (CH), 124.5 (CH), 124.0 (CH), 123.9 (CH), 122.7 (CH), 122.3 (CH), 116.5 (CH), 116.2 (CH), 113.9 (C), 100.8 (C) and 28.8 (CH); *m/z* 410.0791 (M⁺), 290.0536, 289.0493, 262.0626, 121.0287, 120.0221.

6-(4-Acetoxy coumarin-3-yl)-6*H*,7*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-7-one (**3**): A solution of **2** (0.205 g, 5 mmol) in dry pyridine (2 cm³) was heated with acetic anhydride (1 cm³) for 2 h on a water-bath. Then pyridine and excess acetic anhydride were evaporated off under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed over silica gel using gradient elution (petroleum-benzene, 1 : 1) to give the acetate **3** (0.21 g, 93%) in needles, m.p. 238–239° (chloroform-petroleum ether); ν_{max} (KBr)/cm⁻¹ 1725, 1710, 1645, 1630, 1605, 1570, 1270, 1250, 1220, 975, 900, 755; δ_H (CDCl₃, 80 MHz) 8.20–8.00 (2H, m, 5'-H, 12-H), 7.76–7.06 (10H, m, ArH), 5.63 (1H, s, 6-H), 2.45 (3H, s, OAc);

δ_C (CDCl₃, 20 MHz) 167.2 (C), 152.6 (C), 152.4 (C), 149.3 (C), 132.1 (CH), 131.9 (CH), 129.1 (CH), 128.8 (CH), 125.5 (CH), 124.0 (CH), 123.2 (CH), 122.6 (CH), 120.2 (C), 116.6 (CH), 116.4 (CH), 115.8 (C), 99.8 (C), 30.3 (CH) and 20.3 (CH₃).

General procedure for the preparation of 2, 5a-d, 6a, 6b and 7 : 4-Hydroxycoumarin (2 mmol) was heated with aromatic aldehyde (1 mmol) in refluxing dry pyridine (3 cm³) for 24 h under nitrogen or argon atmosphere. Removal of pyridine under reduced pressure afforded the crude product, which was purified by column chromatography over silica gel and then by recrystallisation.

Compound 2 from salicylaldehyde 4a : The benzene eluted fractions afforded **2** (0.346 g, 85%) in needles, m.p. 247° (from chloroform-benzene).

3,4-Dimethoxy-6-(4-hydroxycoumarin-3-yl)-6H,7H-benzopyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-7-one (6a) from 2,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde (4) : The chloroform eluted fractions furnished **6a** (0.385 g, 82%) in needles, m.p. 258° (chloroform-benzene); λ_{\max}/nm 213 (log ϵ 4.92), 264 (4.37), 278 (4.37) and 303 (4.48); ν_{\max} (KBr)/cm⁻¹ 3400, 2990, 1690, 1660, 1630, 1600, 1510, 1485, 1380, 1210, 1195, 755, 750; δ_H (CDCl₃, 80 MHz) 10.3 (1H, br s, OH), 8.17–7.95 (2H, m, 5'-H, 12-H), 7.66–7.24 (6H, m, ArH), 6.87 (1H, s, 5-H), 6.54 (1H, s, 2-H), 5.33 (1H, s, 6-H), 3.93 and 3.78 (2×3H, 2s, 2×OCH₃); δ_C (DMSO, 75 MHz) 161.2 (C), 157.0 (C), 152.6 (C), 152.3 (C), 149.2 (C), 146.8 (C), 143.5 (C), 132.9 (CH), 132.7 (CH), 125.0 (CH), 124.5 (CH), 123.1 (CH), 116.8 (CH), 116.7 (CH), 114.3 (C), 113.0 (C), 111.0 (CH), 101.3 (CH), 56.3 (CH₃) and 29.1 (CH).

*3,4-Methylenedioxy-6-(4-hydroxycoumarin-3-yl)-6H,7H-benzopyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran-7-one (6b) from 6-bromo-3,4-methylenedioxybenzaldehyde (4g)** : The gradient (benzene-chloroform, 2 : 3) eluted fractions gave **6b** (0.3 g, 66%), m.p. 234–235°; λ_{\max}/nm 214 (log ϵ 4.27), 236 (sh. 4.05), 277 (sh. 3.83) and 307 (3.98); ν_{\max} (KBr)/cm⁻¹ 3300, 1710, 1660, 1620, 1490, 1400, 750; δ_H (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) 8.03 and 7.95 (2×1H, 2d, *J* 7.7, 5'-H, 12-H), 7.58–7.12 (6H, m, ArH), 6.74 (1H, s, 5-H), 6.45 (1H, s, 2-H), 5.91 and 5.86 (2H, OCH₂O), 5.21 (1H, s, 6-H); δ_C (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) 161.7 (C), 153.0 (C), 149.0 (C), 145.2 (C), 132.7 (CH), 131.9 (CH), 124.9 (CH), 124.3 (CH), 123.8 (CH), 123.3 (CH), 116.9 (CH), 116.2 (CH), 107.0 (CH), 101.7 (CH₂), 98.3 (CH) and 30.2 (CH).

*3,4-Dimethoxy-6H,7H-benzopyrano[3,2-c][1]benzopyran (7) from 6-bromo-3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (4h)** : The gradient (benzene-chloroform, 1 : 1) eluted fractions afforded **7** (0.21 g, 67.7%), m.p. 180°; λ_{\max}/nm 235

(log ϵ 3.30), 263 (sh. 3.14), 270 (sh. 3.10) and 300 (3.08); ν_{\max} (KBr)/cm⁻¹ 1710, 1660, 1520, 1400, 800; δ_H (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) 7.86 (1H, d, *J* 7.6, 12-H), 7.51–7.20 (3H, m, ArH), 6.67 (1H, s, 5-H), 6.57 (1H, s, 2-H), 3.85 and 3.82 (2×3H, 2s, 2×OCH₃), 3.69 (2H, s, 6-H); δ_C (CDCl₃, 75 MHz), 152.5 (C), 148.8 (C), 131.8 (CH), 124.1 (CH), 122.4 (CH), 116.7 (CH), 111.1 (CH), 100.9 (CH), 56.3 (CH₃), 56.1 (CH₃) and 29.6 (CH₂).

1-(2-Methoxyphenyl)dicoumarol (5a) from 2-methoxybenzaldehyde (4b) : The chloroform eluted fractions gave **5a** (0.331 g, 75%) in needles, m.p. 225–226° (chloroform-benzene); λ_{\max}/nm 211 (log ϵ 4.82), 280 (4.26) and 305 (4.29); ν_{\max} (KBr)/cm⁻¹ 3300, 1690, 1620, 1565, 1490, 1240, 770; δ_H (DMSO, 80 MHz) 8.86 (1H, s, OH), 8.79 (1H, s, OH), 8.43 (2H, m, 5-H), 8.00–6.72 (10H, m, ArH), 6.21 (1H, s), 3.50 (3H, s, OCH₃); δ_C (DMSO, 20 MHz) 166.8 (C), 164.4 (C), 157.4 (C), 152.4 (C), 130.7 (CH), 128.9 (CH), 126.6 (CH), 124.0 (CH), 123.0 (CH), 119.8 (C), 119.6 (C), 115.6 (CH), 111.1 (CH), 104.0 (C), 55.6 (CH₃) and 33.0 (CH).

1-(2-Benzoyloxyphenyl)dicoumarol (5b) from 2-benzoyloxybenzaldehyde (4c) : The gradient (chloroform-benzene, 3 : 1) eluted fractions afforded **5b** (0.373 g, 72%), m.p. 175°; λ_{\max}/nm 214 (log ϵ 4.84), 281 (4.31) and 305 (4.35); ν_{\max} (KBr)/cm⁻¹ 3020, 1655, 1645, 1615, 1600, 1560, 900, 745, 700; δ_H (CDCl₃, 80 MHz) 7.74 (2H, br s, OH), 7.47 (2H, m, 5-H), 7.36–6.70 (15H, m, ArH), 6.01 (1H, s), 4.75 (2H, s, OCH₂); δ_C (CDCl₃, 20 MHz) 167.6 (C), 163.7 (C), 156.6 (C), 151.8 (C), 135.5 (C), 132.0 (CH), 128.2 (CH), 127.8 (CH), 127.5 (CH), 127.2 (CH), 124.2 (CH), 124.0 (CH), 123.4 (CH), 120.3 (C), 116.6 (C), 116.1 (CH), 111.3 (CH), 105.5 (C), 70.0 (CH₂) and 33.3 (CH).

1-(2,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)dicoumarol (5c) from 2,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (4d) : The chloroform eluted fractions furnished **5c** (0.358 g, 76%) in flakes, m.p. 214° (chloroform-benzene); λ_{\max}/nm 211 (log ϵ 4.88), 280 (4.53) and 304 (4.51); δ_H (CDCl₃, 80 MHz) 8.01–7.88 (2H, m, 5-H), 7.61–7.22 (6H, m, ArH), 7.10 (1H, s), 6.52–6.41 (2H, m), 6.02 (1H, s), 3.79 and 3.55 (2×3H, 2s, 2×OCH₃); δ_C (DMSO, 20 MHz) 164.8 (C), 164.2 (C), 159.7 (C), 158.7 (C), 152.3 (C), 133.1 (CH), 132.2 (CH), 124.0 (CH), 123.6 (CH), 117.8 (C), 116.4 (CH), 107.1 (C), 105.3 (C), 104.5 (CH), 99.2 (CH), 56.0 (CH₃), 55.5 (CH₃) and 32.8 (CH).

1-(2,3,4-Trimethoxyphenyl)dicoumarol (5d) from 2,3,4-trimethoxybenzaldehyde (4e) : The chloroform eluted fractions furnished **5d** (0.361 g, 72%) in needles, m.p. 265–266° (chloroform-benzene); λ_{\max}/nm 212 (log ϵ 4.91), 287 (4.37) and 304 (4.41); δ_H (CDCl₃, 80 MHz) 8.03–7.94 (2H, m, 5-H), 7.37–6.58 (8H, m, ArH), 6.23 (1H, s), 3.76,

*The aldehydes **4g** and **4h** were prepared by bromination of piperonal and veratraldehyde respectively

3.62 and 3.31 (3×3H, 3s, 3×OCH₃); δ_C (DMSO, 20 MHz) 164.5 (C), 163.3 (C), 152.5 (C), 152.1 (C), 151.7 (C), 142.1 (C), 132.1 (CH), 124.1 (CH), 123.7 (CH), 122.4 (CH), 117.1 (C), 126.2 (CH), 107.0 (C), 105.6 (CH), 60.2 (CH₃), 55.8 (CH₃) and 32.7 (CH).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank C.S.I.R., U.G.C., New Delhi, and University of Calcutta for providing financial support for this work.

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